

EFaaS: Energy-efficient Function Orchestration in Serverless Edge Computing

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Abstract—Energy in computing is critical as sustainability concerns rise. The serverless edge computing’s energy consumption is significant and growing rapidly. We propose EFaaS, a serverless scheduler that dispatches and caches functions, integrated into an existing serverless platform, reducing the energy cost by jointly considering request dispatching and function caching. We evaluate it using simulations with real-world traces. EFaaS achieves superior performance with 36.5% reduction in energy cost.

Index Terms—Serverless Computing, Edge Computing, Energy Awareness

I. INTRODUCTION

Serverless computing provides lightweight and affordable services under a pay-as-you-go billing model [10, 22], where a complex application is encapsulated into a number of lightweight containers called serverless functions [7]. While recognizing the superiority of serverless edge computing in latency reduction and efficient resource allocation, energy efficiency is now a requirement for sustainable edge computing [15]. The International Energy Agency reported the rapid growth in workloads in large data centers led to a substantial increase in energy consumption between 20–40% annually [2], and Cisco reported that 30% of servers in data centers sit idle worldwide [4]. Service providers and industries are increasingly aiming to improve the sustainability of their operations, reducing the energy consumption and carbon footprint of their systems. Serverless computing could play a pivotal role in this because this novel paradigm could theoretically reclaim the wasted energy in idling servers.

Existing serverless platforms adopt a pay-as-you-go billing model for customers, but cloud providers **bear the costs associated with caching functions** to provide acceptable request service latency. For example, AWS and Azure use a caching policy that retains resources in memory for a fixed period (e.g., 10 and 20 minutes) after a function execution [6]. Thus, it is vitally important for cloud providers to improve energy efficiency while maintaining acceptable latency, making future computing more sustainable.

However, the fixed-time caching policy [21] cannot effectively balance between system performance and energy

Fig. 1. CDF of request inter-arrival times for serverless functions from the Microsoft Azure 14 day trace [1], exhibiting similar patterns.

efficiency: either request service latency is too high for some functions or resources are wasted needlessly caching other functions. Figure 1 illustrates the inter-arrival time of serverless invocations from a Microsoft Azure trace [1] which represents the average time between two successive invocations. Analyzing this dataset, we see that $>59\%$ functions are not invoked within 10 minutes, but also that invocation frequency varies significantly among different functions: the most frequently used functions are invoked 10^8 times more often than the least frequently used ones. The results show that functions exhibit very different invocation patterns and hence it is difficult to predict the arrival pattern. Therefore, it is challenging to determine which functions should be kept alive (cached) by the serverless platform. Ensuring function caching is energy efficient is critical to the overall sustainability of serverless edge computing but is relatively unexplored in the existing literature.

Prior works [8, 19] focus primarily on reducing function

start-up times and cold-start occurrences, exploring a wide range of techniques such as pre-importing packages, sharing image layers and function caching. However, current works largely concentrate on reducing the user-perceived latency by optimizing the cold-start process and overlook the energy consumption in the system [5]. Moreover, existing serverless platforms usually assume a resource-rich cloud, overlooking the distributed and heterogeneous nature of edge computing. Hence, in this work, we focus on energy cost optimization and thus model the energy cost by jointly considering the power price in power grids and the energy consumption of different functions. Then, we propose **EFaaS** which includes a competitive scheduling algorithm and a function caching algorithm, dynamically adapting to the bursty workloads and factoring in multiple important attributes of serverless invocations.

Following an overview of related work (§II) we present the following contributions before concluding (§VI):

- 1) We formulate a serverless request placement problem with function caching as an Integer Linear Programming (ILP) problem, optimizing the energy cost incurred by switching functions, running functions and traffic routing (§III). Also, EFaaS considers the physical topology and resource capacity limit for edge nodes, making it a good fit for edge computing.
- 2) We propose a request scheduling algorithm and a function caching policy that factors in switching cost, invocation frequency and function size. By including those characteristics of serverless invocations, our caching policy exceeds existing caching policies and effectively keeps popular functions alive for future invocations, avoiding repeated creation of functions (§IV).
- 3) We conducted extensive experiments by using real-world topology and datasets. We implemented **EFaaS** in simulations (§V). The experimental results justified that our algorithm achieves superior performance compared to state-of-the-art benchmarks with 36.5% decrease in energy cost.

II. RELATED WORK

a) Optimize the duration of startup process

Wei *et al.* [17] use Remote Direct Memory Access (RDMA) to accelerate container initialization, reducing the tail latency by 89%. Jolteon [23] proposes a stochastic performance model that captures characteristics of serverless executions and performance variability, reducing monetary costs and latency. Xiao *et al.* [19] propose an online lazy caching algorithm with guaranteed performance for serverless functions, jointly considering the startup time, data transmission delay and container caching cost.

b) Optimize the occurrence of cold starts

Some works reduce the occurrence of invoking new containers and hence avoid the cold-start problem, optimizing the end-to-end latency in serverless computing. Flame [20] uses a global cache controller to manage cached functions in serverless computing by ranking functions with hot-scores. Shang *et al.* [14] investigate the container placement and

flow routing problem in serverless computing, considering the heterogeneity and operating overheads of serverless edge computing. Wen *et al.* [18] demonstrate that optimized configuration for serverless workflows can significantly reduce the cold-start overheads by optimizing the memory size for each function step.

c) Optimize the energy consumption in serverless

Aslanpour *et al.* [3] propose an energy-aware algorithm for serverless edge computing but it assumes that edge nodes are only powered by battery and renewable-energy. Stojkovic *et al.* [15] suggest splitting Service Level Objective (SLO) into per-function deadlines and hence minimize the energy consumption. They do not consider the startup process or the network topology and hence their approach does not apply to our problem.

In summary, most existing works focus on reducing the cold-start delay incurred by the startup process but cannot avoid the cold-start issues. Some works aim to reduce the occurrence of cold starts but overlook the energy consumption in serverless computing. Hence, they cannot be directly applied to our problem. A few works focus on energy consumption but do not consider network topology or the startup process of functions. Since efficient management of energy cost is of strategic importance for sustainable edge computing, we decide to investigate the energy cost for serverless edge computing in this work.

III. SYSTEM MODEL & PROBLEM FORMULATION

Service providers deploy services among a set of geographically distributed edge nodes. We use $\mathcal{V} = \{1, 2, \dots, V\}$ to denote the set of edge nodes, $d_{v,v'}$ to represent the traffic routing cost for one unit of traffic between edge nodes v and v' that is proportional to the geographical distance between those edge nodes and $n \in \mathcal{N}$ to represent a serverless request for a type n function. Requests are generated by different end-users. We use a centralized scheduler to orchestrate service requests and assign them to appropriate edge nodes that serve them. The system operates over discrete time slots, with a large number of time slots t spanning a time period \mathcal{T} , $t \in \mathcal{T}$.

Each serverless function n is represented by a container in an edge node, where each replica of the function is referred to as a function instance. Each instance of a function in edge node v comes with a resource capacity denoted by u_n , meaning the required amount of resources for function n . Considering the constrained amount of resources in each edge node, we use U_v to denote the total amount of resources provided by edge node v . Each function n incurs a certain amount of energy cost in the startup process which is denoted by q_v^n . Also, we introduce $c_v(t)$ to represent the energy price in edge node v which is time-varying. Similarly, energy consumption is incurred by running a function in edge node v denoted by p_v^n for one time slot.

To denote the decision variables of the system, we further use $x_v^n(t)$ to denote the number of type n requests dispatched to the edge node v in time slot t . Similarly, let $y_{v,v'}^n(t)$ represent the number of type n requests, which originate from

node v and assigned to a neighbor node v' in time slot t . In a given time slot, we use $b_v^n(t)$ to denote the number of cached type n functions in edge node v and $a_v^n(t)$ for the number of active functions at node v , namely the functions are executing tasks. Additionally, we use $\delta_v^n(t)$ to represent the total number of type n requests originate from edge node v in the time slot t .

A. Cost structure

- 1) *Container Running Cost.* Let p_v^n denote the power consumption of running a container n for one time slot. Then, the total container running cost at time slot t is formulated by:

$$C_R(t) = \sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} p_v^n \cdot c_v(t) \cdot x_v^n(t). \quad (1)$$

where $c_v(t)$ represents the energy price on edge node v in the time slot t .

- 2) *Container Switching Cost.* Launching a new container n necessitates downloading a container image to the hosting edge node, spinning up the container and loading the package code in memory. We use q_v^n to denote the cost of deploying a newly created container n at edge cloud v . Then, the total switching cost at time slot t is given by:

$$C_S(t) = \sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} q_v^n \cdot [x_v^n(t) - b_v^n(t)]^+. \quad (2)$$

where $[x_v^n(t) - b_v^n(t)]^+ = \max\{x_v^n(t) - b_v^n(t), 0\}$, denoting the number of newly created type n containers in time slot t .

- 3) *Traffic Routing Cost.* When routing the traffic of various containers, the traffic routing cost is incurred by the energy usage of forwarding and routing network traffic. This is primarily determined by the source and destination location of edge nodes. Thus, we use a cost parameter $d_{v,v'}$ to represent the cost of routing one unit of traffic from edge node v to v' .

$$C_T(t) = \sum_{v,v' \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} d_{v,v'} \cdot h_n \cdot y_{v,v'}^n(t). \quad (3)$$

where h_n denotes the amount of traffic for request n and $y_{v,v'}^n(t)$ represents the number of requests originating from node v and offloaded to node v' .

B. The cost minimization problem

In this work, we formulate a request scheduling and function caching problem, aiming to optimize the energy cost incurred by function running, function switching and traffic routing in serverless edge computing.

Problem 1:

$$\min \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \left(C_R(t) + C_S(t) + C_T(t) \right), \quad (4)$$

s.t.,

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} u_n \left(\max\{x_v^n(t), b_v^n(t)\} + a_v^n(t) \right) \leq U_v, \forall v \in \mathcal{V}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (5)$$

$$x_v^n(t) + \sum_{v' \in \mathcal{V}} y_{v,v'}^n(t) = \delta_v^n(t), \forall v \in \mathcal{V}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (6)$$

$$x_v^n(t), y_{v,v'}^n(t) \in \{0, 1, \dots, \delta_v^n\}, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, v \in \mathcal{V}. \quad (7)$$

Eq. 5 ensures that the resources required by active and cached containers must not exceed the maximum resource capacity on each edge node. Eq. 6 ensures that all requests must be allocated to an edge node. Eq. 7 guarantees the integrality for the number of distributed requests $x_v^n(t)$ and $y_{v,v'}^n(t)$.

IV. SOLUTION

A. Algorithm design

In this section, we design a request dispatch algorithm that achieves constant approximation to the proposed problem. Also, we devised a caching algorithm based on function priority.

B. Request dispatch

As illustrated in Algorithm 1, to offload requests to the nearby edge nodes, we first sort all neighbor nodes v' in ascending order according to $d_{v,v'}$. After that, we update the priorities for each type of serverless function in the system according to the equation 8. Next, if $\delta_v^n(t) \leq b_v^n(t)$, which indicates there are sufficient containers cached in node v to handle the incoming requests, the algorithm will assign all requests to the cached containers (Lines 6-9).

Otherwise, if $\delta_v^n(t) > b_v^n(t)$, the algorithm uses cached containers to accommodate part of the incoming requests which is $x_v^n(t) \leftarrow b_v^n(t)$ (Lines 10-12). After that, there are still $k_v^n(t)$ requests to be served in the system. In this case, the algorithm starts to iterate over the list of neighbor nodes \mathcal{V}' , exploring the opportunities to assign requests to neighbor nodes (Line 13-21). The philosophy is that if the traffic routing cost $d_{v,v'} \cdot h_n$ is less than the switching cost q_v^n indicated by Line 14, the algorithm will attempt to use cached containers in edge node v' . If one neighbor node v' cannot accommodate the requests left, the algorithm will iterate to the next neighbor nodes with available cached containers (Line 20-21). Eventually, if there are still requests remaining to be served, the algorithm will invoke Algorithm 2 to make space for launching new containers at the current node v (Lines 25-26).

As illustrated in Algorithm 2, to create new containers, we need to destroy the container with the lowest priority until there is sufficient capacity for a particular container. The priority is calculated based on equation 8.

C. Function caching policy

We propose a function caching policy by using Equation 8 to calculate the priority for each function. When an edge node is overloaded, we compute a ‘‘priority’’ for each function based

Algorithm 1: Request Dispatch

```
1 foreach  $t \in \mathcal{T}$  do
2   foreach  $v \in \mathcal{V}$  do
3     foreach  $n \in \mathcal{N}$  do
4       Sort all nodes  $v'$  by  $d_{v,v'}$  in ascending
5       order in the sorted list  $\mathcal{V}'$ .
6       Calculate the priority of type  $n$  function
7       acc. to Equation 8.
8       if  $\delta_v^n(t) \leq b_v^n(t)$  then
9         Assign all  $\delta_v^n(t)$  requests to current
10        node  $v$ .
11         $x_v^n(t) \leftarrow \delta_v^n(t)$ .
12         $k_v^n(t) \leftarrow 0$ .
13      else if  $\delta_v^n(t) > b_v^n(t)$  then
14         $x_v^n(t) \leftarrow b_v^n(t)$ .
15         $k_v^n(t) \leftarrow \delta_v^n(t) - b_v^n(t)$ .
16        foreach  $v' \in \mathcal{V}'$  do
17          if  $d_{v,v'} \cdot h_n \leq q_v^n$  then
18            if  $b_{v'}^n(t) \geq k_{v'}^n(t)$  then
19               $y_{v,v'}^n(t) \leftarrow k_{v'}^n(t)$ .
20               $k_{v'}^n(t) \leftarrow 0$ .
21              break;
22            else
23               $y_{v,v'}^n(t) \leftarrow b_{v'}^n(t)$ .
24               $k_{v'}^n(t) \leftarrow k_{v'}^n(t) - b_{v'}^n(t)$ .
25            end
26          end
27        end
28      end
29    end
30  end
31 end
```

Algorithm 2: Launch New Containers

```
1 Update priority for all containers acc. to equation 8.
2 while  $\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} u_n(x_v^n(t) + a_v^n(t)) > U_v$  do
3   Destroy the container with the lowest priority.
4 end
5 Create a new type  $n$  container for the request;
```

on cost, resource footprint and frequency, and terminate the function with the lowest priority.

Priority calculation: Our **EFaaS** policy is inspired by a content caching policy [9] initially devised for content with different sizes such as documents. The proposed EFaaS algorithm is conscious of the frequency and switching cost of different functions, making it an adaptive approach to the burstiness and high concurrency in serverless computing.

Essentially, our function caching algorithm is a function termination policy. EFaaS decides which function to terminate if a new function needs to be created and there are insufficient hardware resources available in the edge node. This idea derives from the current time-to-live policies implemented in serverless platforms and public clouds that keep functions alive for a while. The priority calculation is given in Equation 8, due to its simplicity, the various inputs (i.e., Freq, Size and Switching cost) are immediately available after execution and hence our caching policy is completely online.

$$Priority = \frac{Freq(t) \cdot SwitchingCost}{Size}. \quad (8)$$

Freq(t) refers to the number of invocations a particular function is called so far.

SwitchingCost refers to the container switching cost incurred by pulling an image to a host server and initializing the environment before serving requests.

Size refers to the memory usage of a function because a function loads code to the memory.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

We conducted experiments with trace-driven simulations. Experimental results justify the efficacy of EFaaS with a real-world topology and energy prices in different zones of New York State.

Fig. 2. Graphical map of edge servers in New York State

A. Simulation setup

- 1) **Infrastructure:** As shown in Figure 2, we simulate an edge network that consists of 76 edge servers in New York State derived from the Geospatial Management Office for New York State [12]. We conducted the simulation in a server with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) E5645 processor of 24 cores and 105GB RAM.
- 2) **Workload trace:** We use the Azure dataset [1] to create the pattern of serverless requests. This dataset includes the invocations of serverless functions in Microsoft Azure for 14 days. The workload in each edge node is generated based on the Zipf Distribution, which is widely used in edge computing, with an exponent β over 0.5, 0.75 and 1.0. Different β values indicate different workloads in the system where generally the workloads decrease when β increases.
- 3) **Containers:** We have selected four containers from the literature [16] that report the power consumption, namely

Fig. 3. CDF of energy cost in simulation

Fig. 4. Average energy and switching cost in simulation

Nginx, Ubuntu, Python, Debian. The power consumption of these containers ranges from 15 to 18 watts. Also, the container size ranges between 26 and 353 MB. We selected the top four functions in the dataset that are most popular and mapped them to those four containers.

- 4) **System parameters:** For the container running cost, the energy price $c_v(t)$ is derived from New York Energy Market [11] for 24 hours. For the cross-edge traffic routing cost $d_{v,v'}$, we consider it is proportional to the geographical distance, and the total traffic routing cost $C_T(t)$ is in a similar order of magnitude to the container running cost $C_R(t)$. Also, for the switching cost parameter q_v^n , we set it to make the switching cost $C_S(t)$ have a similar order of magnitude to $C_R(t)$.

- 5) **Performance benchmark:** We selected three widely used algorithms from the literature as follows.

- a) **Hybrid** is a popular function caching algorithm proposed by [13] to mitigate cold-start issues. Hybrid relies on the invocation patterns of applications. By using the invocation history, it decides on pre-warming and destroying containers. Hybrid is particularly suitable for invocations that show a clear pattern.
- b) **LRU** adopts the philosophy of Least Recently Used

caching. Each container is labeled with a timestamp and the one, that is least recently used, will be evicted from the cache.

- c) **FC** represents Fixed Caching which is widely adopted by cloud providers such as AWS Lambda functions. In this paper, FC caches each container for 10 minutes.

B. Results in simulation

First, we show the performance simulated in a topology with 76 nodes as illustrated in Figure 2. In the simulation, we present three key metrics to evaluate the system performance, namely the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of energy cost, the average switching cost and the average energy cost in monetary form. As aforementioned, we conducted experiments over 3 different zipf- β values to justify the performance under different workloads.

CDF of energy cost in simulation: Figure 3 shows the CDF of energy costs under different workloads. We observe that EFaaS shows the best performance in the considered scenario because it jointly considers the cost and invocation frequency of functions that significantly reduces the energy cost. The 95th percentile energy costs of EFaaS are \$133.65, \$292.06 and \$125.46, respectively. LRU yields 95th percentile energy

cost at \$681.12, \$626.02 and \$586.90, respectively. While not exciting, these results were expected because LRU only considers the recency of serverless invocations and overlooks other characteristics associated with serverless functions such as resource footprint. Hybrid is outperformed by LRU because Hybrid largely relies on a clear invocation pattern of serverless functions. Finally, FC performs worse compared to other algorithms with the 95th percentile at \$685.05, \$678.18 and \$626.02 under different workloads. The rationale is that FC adopts a simple but static caching algorithm that cannot adapt to the burstiness and concurrency in serverless computing.

Avg. energy and switching cost in simulation: Figure 4 shows the average energy cost and switching cost. Note that high switching cost is incurred by frequent launching of new containers which is part of the energy cost. If the switching cost increases, it will contribute a considerable amount to the total energy cost. We observe that EFaaS shows the best performance whose average energy cost and switching cost are \$100.60 and \$10.87 when $\beta = 0.5$. The results suggest that EFaaS caches a pool of containers based on several intrinsic attributes of serverless workloads and is more likely to reuse popular containers in the near future. We also notice that the switching costs of LRU, Hybrid and FC are significantly greater than that of EFaaS over 3 different workloads. For instance, the switching cost of LRU are \$128.91, \$80.10 and \$40.67 while that of EFaaS are only \$10.87, \$12.31 and \$8.91, respectively. These results indicate that EFaaS efficiently reduces the occurrence of launching new functions because the proposed caching policy is more likely to cache popular containers that will be invoked in the near future.

VI. CONCLUSION

We investigated the minimization problem of energy cost in serverless edge computing, showing it to be NP-hard. We proposed an online algorithm that provides performance guarantees taking into account both the distributed and heterogeneous nature of edge computing, and the burstiness and high concurrency of serverless computing. Using a prototype implementation and extensive simulation, we demonstrate the efficacy of our approach, achieving superior performance with 36.5% reduction in energy cost. The key feature of EFaaS is that it adapts dynamically to the time-varying workloads and the arrival pattern by including several important attributes of serverless workloads.

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